

AN ACOUSTO-ULTRASONICS PATTERN RECOGNITION APPROACH FOR THE CHARACTERIZATION OF THE RESIDUAL IMPACT PROPERTIES OF A CLASS OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The nondestructive Acousto-Ultrasonics (AU) technique is used, in conjunction with Pattern Recognition (PR) and Classification methods, for the characterization of the residual impact properties of a class of composite system; namely graphite/polycarbonate composite. Material specimens of different low-energy repeated-impact are processed by acousto-ultrasonics and describing features of the retrieved signals are used to build Pattern Recognition Classifiers. These classifiers are, then, employed to identify unknown impact-damage states in other specimens of the material. The destructive Falling Impact Test is used to verify and correlate with the AU measurements.

INTRODUCTION

Impact loading of polymeric base structural members may degrade their mechanical response characteristics without changes in visual appearance or the presence of overt flaws in the material. The same could occur when the member is subjected to low-energy impact that is applied in a repeated manner. Hence, it is important to predict at the design stage the impact-strength reduction of the material involved for given low-energy repeated-impact loading. Moreover, for a structural member already in service under repeated-impact loading, it is often necessary to estimate quantitatively how much its structural ability to withstand subsequent impact loading might have been affected.

The main objective of the presented research is to assess the feasibility of evaluating nondestructively, in a quantitative manner, low-energy repeated-impact damage in a polymeric base composite system, i.e. a Graphite fibre/Polycarbonate matrix system. This is carried out using the relatively new non-destructive Acousto-ultrasonic technique, in conjunction with

Falling Impact Test is used to verify and correlate with the predictions of the AU testing results.

The structure of the chosen composite comprises two exterior graphite-fibre woven fabric/polycarbonate in [(0/90)₄] configuration and enclosing a 1.58 mm-core of polycarbonate. The test specimens are machined from a single sheet of 3.3 mm of thickness and each has external dimensions of 25.4 mm x 108mm.

CONTROLLED REPEATED IMPACT DAMAGE

The purpose of this procedure is to obtain specimens of controlled repeated-impact damage levels, where the level of impact damage on each specimen is determined by the number of falling-weight impacts applied onto it. Specimens subjected to the same level of repeated-impact constitute a sample representing this impact condition for the purposes of the subsequent non-destructive and destructive tests. Different levels of controlled low-energy impact damage are obtained by using a specially designed device [1] whereby a constant weight (0.4 kg) is dropped from a fixed height (0.75 m), onto a clamped material specimen, a predetermined number of times. Six levels of repeated-impact damage are obtained, namely, 0, 1, 3, 4, 6 and 10 impacts.

After impacting the specimen by the predetermined number of impacts, it was visually examined for any apparent failure. In this case, the specimen in question is excluded from subsequent non-destructive and destructive testing programs.

ACOUSTO-ULTRASONIC TECHNIQUE

Acousto-ultrasonics is a relatively new non-destructive technique that has been used successfully in estimating mechanical response characteristics of materials, particularly those that show high attenuation of ultrasonic waves, e.g. polymeric materials and polymeric-base composite systems. For this class of materials, traditional non-destructive testing has proven, on the other hand, to be unsuccessful.

Acousto-ultrasonics may be taken as standing for "acoustic emission simulation with ultrasonic sources", [2]. Instead of loading the specimen to excite spontaneous stress waves in the microstructure as in Acoustic Emission methods, AU uses external ultrasonic sources to resemble AE waves without disrupting destructively the material.

The working hypothesis of the AU technique is that more efficient strain energy transfer and strain redistribution during mechanical loading would correspond to increased mechanical strength of the material. This hypothesis is based on the stress-wave interaction concept. It holds that stress waves at the onset of material fracture would promote rapid cracking unless their energy is efficiently transmitted through the microstructure.

AU relies on stochastic wave propagation in the material. That is, depending on the physical and geometrical characteristics of the material specimen, multiple, reflected, scattered and mode-converted waves form the output signal. The latter is, thus, a highly modulated signal that is generally composed of numerous components.

A diagram of an AU testing set-up, used in the present work, is shown in Figure 1. In this, an ultrasonic pulsar is employed to periodically excite a sending transducer. The pulse repetition rate is set by a Repetition Rate Controller. The pulse triggers the Time Base Generator to

synchronize the sweep of the Waveform Digitizer with the output of the receiver probe. It is usually necessary for the output of the receiver to be preamplified before entering the Vertical Amplifier. The amplified signal is passed to the Waveform Digitizer where it is transformed from analogical to digital. Both the analogical signal and the signal from the Time Base Generator are used as inputs to a Display Terminal for the Visualization of the signal in time-domain. The analogical signal is eventually passed to a waveform storage medium and a waveform data analysis system.

Although the sender transducer injects longitudinal waves propagating in a normal direction to the surface of the test specimen, it is expected that the injected pulses would produce oblique reflections and shear waves. AU components of the propagating signal are to interact with the microstructure of the material.

Figure 1. The AU-experimental set-up [1].

The set of controlled parameters that are used for testing the graphite/polycarbonate composite specimens is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. AU controlled parameters for graphite/polycarbonate composite specimens.

TYPE OF PARAMETER	CONTROLLED PARAMETER	SET VALUE
EXTERNAL	- Distance between Transducer	31.8 mm (1.25")
	- Couplant Medium	UltrageI II™
INTERNAL	- Voltage Range	0 to + 12 Volts
	- Gain	26 deciBels
	- Wave Frequency	750 KHZ

PATTERN RECOGNITION AND CLASSIFICATION APPROACH

The interaction of the emitted ultrasonic waves with the material microstructure result in quite complex AU waveforms. Thus, the extraction of useful information from such signal could be, in general, a difficult task.

In the present work, analysis of AU signals is carried out by multivariate extraction and classification. Here, Pattern Recognition (PR) and Classification methodology offers an appropriate approach for the multivariate analysis of AU signals. In developing the theory and techniques to perform a given recognition task, Pattern Recognition and Classification may be defined as the categorization of input data into identifiable classes via the extraction of significant features or attributes from a background of relevant data.

There are several mathematical tools that can be used for the analysis of Pattern Recognition and Classification problems. The choice of a number of these tools to analyze a particular collection of data defines a procedure. Such a procedure is often referred to as the "design of a PR-system". In this context, it is convenient to deal with the pattern recognition problem in three spaces; namely,

- the Pattern Space P_s ,
- the Feature Space F_s , and
- the Classification Space C_s

The collection of data values pertaining to the retrieved AU signals from the test specimens forms the Pattern Space P_s . In order to reduce the dimensionality of the Pattern Space while maintaining the discriminatory power between the different patterns, a Feature Space F_s is established from the Pattern Space by reducing the number of describing parameters. As the ultimate purpose of a designed Pattern Recognition and Classification system is the identification of a given pattern as belonging to one of the classes under consideration, a classification space must be established. The latter is the "decision space" in which one of the defined classes is selected.

In an operational format, the pattern recognition problem can be described as a transformation from the Pattern Space P_s , to the Feature Space F_s , and then, finally, to the Classification Space C_s . This transformation may be expressed as

$$P_s \rightarrow F_s \rightarrow C_s \quad (1)$$

Therefore, the design of a Pattern Recognition System is the establishment of a procedure, or eventually a sequence of procedures, to perform the transformation (1), see, e.g., [3, 4].

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Characterization of Repeated-Impact Properties by Falling-Weight Impact Test.

A Falling-Weight Impact Test, as per ASTM D3029-Method G [5], was performed for each sample of eight specimens pertaining to each of the controlled repeated-impact damage levels considered.

Statistical analysis of the outcome of passes and fails from the testing of each sample of specimens is carried out by the so-called Up-and-Down Method [1]. This method gives

estimates of the mean, called Mean Failure Energy (MFE) of the distribution of impact failure energy pertaining to each level of impact. Figure 2 presents the obtained estimates of MFE versus the corresponding levels of repeated impact, as measured by the final number of repeated impacts. A correlation factor of 0.98 is obtained by a straight line fitting through the data points of Figure 2.

Figure 2. "Mean Failure Energy" versus number of repeated impacts [1].

Characterization of Repeated-Impact Properties by Acousto-Ultrasonics.

Acousto-Ultrasonics Parameter (AUP) [6] values are calculated of the AU readings from the test specimens as pertaining to known levels of controlled low-energy repeated impact. At each level of impact, the average value of AUP for the sample of specimens is calculated of the measured values of AUP for the specimens of this sample. All obtained AUP values are, then, normalized as per Equation (2) below

$$AUP_N = \frac{AUP}{\text{Maximum average AUP}} \quad (2)$$

where,

AUP is either the measured Acousto-Ultrasonics Parameter for a test specimen or the calculated "average of AUP" for a sample of specimens.

"Maximum average AUP" is the largest value calculated from the averages of AUP for all samples of test specimens. It is found to represent the average of AUP values for the "no-impact" level sample.

AUP_N is the pertaining value of normalized AUP.

Further, the MFE values for the different levels of impact considered were normalized as per the following relation

$$MFE_N = \frac{MFE}{\text{Maximum MFE}} \quad (3)$$

where,

MFE is the value of Mean Failure Energy for a level of impact.

"Maximum MFE" is the largest observed value of MFE of the calculated MFE values for all samples of specimens. It corresponds to the MFE value for the "no-impact" level sample considered.

Figure 3 presents the normalized AUP values versus normalized Mean Failure Energy values for the tested samples. A correlation factor of 0.94 is obtained by a straight line fitting through the data points of Figure 3.

Figure 3. "Normalized AUP" versus "Normalized MFE".

Pattern Recognition and Classification Analysis.

For PR purposes, the retrieved AU-signals are grouped in classes, each representing one of the considered states of impact damage. The following three classes are considered:

- Class A: No impacts
- Class B: Three impacts
- Class C: Ten impacts

The retrieved AU signals pertaining to each class are divided in two sets; namely, "Classifier" and "Training" sets. The "Classifier" sets are used for building the classifiers, as well as for further testing of "Training" and "Evaluation" performances. "Testing" sets are used for testing of the "Classification" performance. To carry out the feature extraction and normalization procedures, both Classifier and Training sets have to be arranged in the so-called "file-trees", respectively labelled "Classifier Tree" and "Normalization Tree". Classifier and Normalization trees are used by the adopted software to extract and normalize "feature-files" for the different classes under consideration. Each feature file comprises the characteristic feature values of the AU-signals for the identification of the pertaining class.

The used software extracts 108 feature values from each digitalized record of an AU-signal. These values are of diverse order of magnitude in five domains of waveform description; namely, time, feature, phase, cepstral and auto correlation domains. Thus, feature normalization is necessary in order to make the results pertaining to the different domains comparable in an N-feature space. In this work, normalization is performed by means of the "Method of Zero-Mean Unit Variance Mapping", see, e.g., [7, 8]. On carrying out the experimental work, it was

revealed that, given a limited size sample of AU signals from a limited number of material specimens, the normalization outcome depends on the set of AU signals that is chosen to perform the normalization. This set of AU signals is defined by the choice of both the "Classifier" and "Normalization" trees to normalize the "Classifier" and "Testing" sets, respectively.

With the use of significantly large number of features for describing the AU signals, the problem of selecting an optimal set of best discriminating features could be very complex. In this work, a procedure was designed that establishes the classifier of the highest average of the classification performances, for the classes under consideration. For each particular classification problem, it is possible to determine a ranking of feature's discriminating ability between the classes in question. In this context, the following classifiers are designed:

- (i) Empirical Bayesian Classifier (designed for the four best-ranked features).
- (ii) Linear Discriminant Classifier (designed for the four best-ranked features).
- (iii) K-Nearest Classifier (based on the three best-ranked features).
- (iv) Minimum Distance Classifier (based on the two best-ranked features).

Excellent Training and Evaluation performances were obtained for the classifiers mentioned above. Also, it was found that, for each classifier, both the training and evaluation performances are quite close and do not differ from each other by more than few percentages. This may be taken as an indication of high AU-signal repeatability for the same specimen as well as specimens of the same level of impact damage. Figure 4 displays the normalized values for the first and the second best ranked features, while Figure 5 presents the normalized values for the second and the third best ranked features in the Classifier Sets. These normalized feature values reflect clusters of values of the used features, whereby each cluster represents one of the considered impact classes.

X1 : Normalized feature values of second-ranked feature.
 X2 : Normalized feature values of first-ranked feature.

Figure 4. Normalized values for the first and the second best ranked features from AU-signals pertaining to three repeated impact damage states [1].

X1 : Normalized feature values of second-ranked feature.

X2 : Normalized feature values of third-ranked feature.

Figure 5. Normalized values for the second and the third best ranked features from AU-signals pertaining to three repeated impact damage states [1].

With reference to Figures 4 and 5, one observes that the used features are able to discriminate between the different levels of impact damage. The two figures show further that the clusters of normalized feature values pertaining to classes B and C of impact-damage are closer to each other than to class A of undamaged specimens.

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